

RDA Council

Minutes of Meetings 2023

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RDA Council Meeting

25th January 2023 UTC 12:00-13:30

Meeting Chair: Jill Benn

Attendees:

1. Jill Benn
2. Louise Bezuidenhout
3. Juan Bicarregui
4. Sandra Collins
5. Ingrid Dillo
6. Francoise Genova
7. Jason Haga
8. Edit Herczog
9. Rebecca Koskela
10. Claudia Medeiros
11. Isabelle Perseil
12. Shelley Stall
13. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
14. Connie Clare (RDA Foundation Community Development Manager)
15. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation Operations & Accounts Manager) (notes)

Apologies: Joyce Gosata Maphanyane, Robert Hanisch, Rob Quick, Lee Wilson

Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 3-4 November 2022

Discussion:

Outstanding actions were discussed with update on progress and completion. No Council members expressed any conflicts of interest with the agenda items.

RDA Strategic Plan 2024-2028 – Jill Benn

Discussion:

Council discussed the next steps for the RDA Strategic Plan 2024-2028 taking into consideration the 2023 priorities and a 5 year vision. Council discussed the 3 pillars, considering any appropriate changes.

Decision:

Council agreed a 4th Pillar would be included. The process of the Strategic Plan will involve sharing content with the RDA community at RDA Plenary 20, March 2023 and gathering feedback to be incorporated to the Plan. A draft of the new strategy to be drawn up prior to release at RDA Plenary 21, October 2023.

RDA 20th Plenary Meeting – Hilary Hanahoe, Ingrid Dillo

Discussion:

Council was presented with an update of the RDA P20 status and the programme. Agenda items for a face to face Council meeting at P20 were proposed.

RDA Foundation Financial Update – Jason Haga

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the RDA F cashflow 2022 and forecasts for 2023.

RDA Regional Engagement 2023 – Hilary Hanahoe

Discussion:

Council was presented with an update on the status of regional engagement for 2023 highlighting particular aspects for Africa, the Americas, Asia, the Middle East, Europe and Oceania.

AOB

Council Nominations Committee 2023 – Sandra Collins

Web Platform Update – Hilary Hanahoe

TAB Elections Update – Isabelle Perseil

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the Council Nominations Committee and the new election process to be implemented for the first time in the 2023 elections.

Hilary provided an update on the status of the web platform development confirming an update will be given to the RDA community at P20.

Isabelle Perseil presented the results of the TAB elections, confirming the new members and those who would be ending their terms.

RDA Council Meeting
20th March 2023 UTC 08:00-11:00
RDA P20, Gothenburg, Sweden

Meeting Chair: Jill Benn / Ingrid Dillo

Attendees:

1. Jill Benn
2. Louise Bezuidenhout
3. Juan Bicarregui
4. Sandra Collins
5. Ingrid Dillo
6. Francoise Genova
7. Jason Haga
8. Robert Hanisch
9. Edit Herczog
10. Rebecca Koskela
11. Joyce Gosata Maphanyane
12. Claudia Medeiros
13. Isabelle Perseil
14. Rob Quick
15. Shelley Stall
16. Lee Wilson
17. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
18. Kathryn Barker (RDA Community Development Manager – ARDC)
19. Connie Clare (RDA Foundation Community Development Manager)
20. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation Operations & Accounts Manager) (notes)

Apologies:

Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 3-4 November 2022

Discussion:

Outstanding actions were discussed with update on progress and completion. No Council members expressed any conflicts of interest with the agenda items.

Executive Committee Meeting Update

Discussion and Decision:

The elected council members and legal entity representative agreed and approved the Secretary General's proposal to make the RDA Foundation Operations & Accounts Manager and RDA Foundation Community Development manager's contracts permanent with

immediate effect. The Financial Subcommittee's policy on inflation for the RDA Foundation staff contracts was also approved.

Council Nominations 2023 Progress & Update – Sandra Collins

Discussion:

The Chair of the Council nominations committee presented the status of the nominations for the 2023 Council elections confirming five eligible candidates will progress to the election process which, for the first time, will see the RDA community voting for the individual candidates. All RDA members will be invited to vote for four of the five candidates.

RDA Foundation Financial Update – FSC Chair, Edit Herczog

Discussion:

Council was provided with a summary of the RDA Foundation financial status for the first quarter of 2023 and a conservative forecast for 2025-2028, highlighting that expenditure has been tracked well with a winddown scenario showing the situation precisely.

RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB) Update – Rob Quick

Discussion:

The co-chair of TAB provided an update of the face-to-face meeting which took place the previous day in Gothenburg with 9 TAB members attending.

Decision:

Following discussions from the points raised, including TAB liaisons to groups, TAB engagement with group outputs, cross-group coordination and plenary planning, it was decided an agenda item should be included at the next Council meeting to discuss the proposals.

2024-2028 Strategy – Ingrid Dillo, Jill Benn

Discussion:

Council discussed the community consultation actions to take place during P20, including an overview of the ideas to be presented at the Business Session during Plenary session 5 – Building the RDA Community for the Future. A brainstorming session was held in Pillar Sub-Groups on the 4 Strategy Pillars, Globalise, Sustain, Lead, and Innovate with the aim of generating ideas and activities to define the direction of the RDA.

Decision:

The priorities resulting from the brainstorming session to be embedded in the strategy document for the next Council meeting.

RDA Council Meeting

26th April 2023 UTC 11:30-13:00

Meeting Chair: Ingrid Dillo

Attendees:

1. Jill Benn
2. Juan Bicarregui
3. Sandra Collins
4. Ingrid Dillo
5. Francoise Genova
6. Jason Haga
7. Bob Hanisch
8. Edit Herczog
9. Rebecca Koskela
10. Shelley Stall
11. Lee Wilson
12. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)

Apologies: Louise Bezuidenhout, Connie Clare, Joyce Gosata Maphanyane, Claudia Medeiros, Isabelle Perseil, Rob Quick, Bridget Walker

Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 3-4 November 2022

Discussion:

Outstanding actions were discussed with update on progress and completion. No Council members expressed any conflicts of interest with the agenda items.

RDA Strategic Plan 2024-2028 Update – Jill Benn

Discussion:

The discussion point involved an analysis of P20 and online community feedback, a recap of major outcomes and an outline of a roadmap for the next steps up to P21 in October 2023. Council members agreed on the allocated subgroups for the 4 strategy Pillars to be assisted by Secretariat members.

TAB Report / Plans – Isabelle Perseil, Rob Quick, TAB Co-chairs

Discussion:

Hilary Hanahoe (Secretary General) presented, on behalf of the TAB co-chairs, a summary report of the TAB face to face meeting which took place prior to the RDA P20 in

Gothenburg, Sweden 19 March 2023. A discussion on proposed actions and modifications within TAB followed.

Decision:

In an attempt to resolve the issue of inactive groups, TAB would provide an update on the criteria and procedures for managing such groups.

RDA 10 x 10 Taskforce – Juan Bicarregui

Discussion:

Council discussed the proposal for an official taskforce or similar, to look at factors limiting the growth of the RDA and how it could look in 10 years if, in that time, it grows 10-fold. A timeline and involvement of governance bodies was considered with proposed steps presented.

Decision:

An RDA 10 x 10 small group will draft an overview paper to circulate to Council prior to the next meeting when a decision on the feasibility and eventual creation of such a taskforce will be made.

Global South Taskforce – Hilary Hanahoe

Discussion:

Council discussed the proposal for a taskforce focusing on the Global South / Southern hemisphere in support of the 2023 strategic plan priority and to prepare for the 2024-2028 Southern hemisphere focus. Definition of the Global South, scope and process and proposed steps and timing were presented to Council.

Decision:

Council approves the creation of the taskforce and Hilary will take forward as per the steps and timing presented.

AOB

RDA OfR WG

Discussion:

Council discussed the concern for the potential overlap and duplication of efforts between the newly proposed WG and the NIST RDaF Framework, as expressed by a Council member.

Decision:

A meeting would be set up between those concerned to define the RDA-OfR WG case statement synchronisation and complementarity to NIST RDaF.

RDA Council Meeting 19th July 2023 UTC 11:30-13:00

Meeting Chair: Jill Benn

Attendees:

1. Jill Benn
2. Louise Bezuidenhout
3. Juan Bicarregui
4. Joyce Gosata Maphanyane
5. Jason Haga
6. Francoise Genova
7. Wolfram Horstmann
8. Claudia Medeiros
9. Amy Nurnberger
10. Isabelle Perseil
11. Rob Quick
12. Shelley Stall
13. Lee Wilson
14. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
15. Connie Clare (RDA Foundation Community Development Manager)
16. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation Operations & Accounts Manager) (notes)

Apologies: Ingrid Dillo, Rebecca Koskela

Executive Committee Meeting 11:30-12:00

Elected RDA Council members and STFC representative, Juan Bicarregui discussed the Secretary General's annual performance review which received extremely positive feedback. New Council roles and responsibilities following the changeover of members were proposed and discussed and the Committee supported the following nominations:

- Lee Wilson as RDA Council Co-chair,
- Juan Bicarregui as Chair of the Financial Subcommittee
- Amy Nurnberger as member of the Financial Sub-Committee.

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 26 April 2023](#)

Discussion:

Outstanding actions were discussed with update on progress and completion.

No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed.

New Council members, Amy Nurnberger and Wolfram Horstmann were welcomed, together with Joyce Gosata for her re-election.

RDA Strategic Plan 2024-2028 Update – Jill Benn and Pillar Representatives

Discussion:

The representatives of each strategy pillar, Globalise, Sustain, Leadership and Innovate provided an update on the strategic areas, priorities, time period, projects, initiatives and actions within each Pillar.

Decision:

Lee, Jill, Hilary and Connie to bring all 4 pillars together and put together a draft strategy by September 2023.

RDA Foundation Financial Update – Juan Bicarregui

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the RDA F cashflow April-June 2023 and forecasts 2023-2028. The position of the Foundation's accounts remains similar to previous years except the situation is now more stable.

AOB

Council was informed of the full day face to face Council meeting scheduled for Friday 27th October 2023, following IDW 2023 in Salzburg, Austria.

It was decided the Council meeting in September would be held to finalise the strategy document.

Hilary informed Council of the delay in the launch of the new platform from June to November and that an announcement would be made. The complexity of the work requires more time, but no further costs would be involved.

RDA Council Meeting

7th September 2023 UTC 11:00-12:30

Meeting Chair: Lee Wilson

Attendees:

1. Ingrid Dillo
2. Jason Haga
3. Francoise Genova
4. Jason Haga
5. Sarah Jones
6. Rebecca Koskela
7. Claudia Medeiros
8. Amy Nurnberger
9. Isabelle Perseil
10. Rob Quick
11. Shelley Stall
12. Lee Wilson
13. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
14. Connie Clare (RDA Foundation Community Development Manager)(notes)

Apologies: Jill Benn, Louise Bezuidenhout, Juan Bicarregui, Joyce Gosata Maphanyane, Wolfram Horstmann, Bridget Walker

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 19 July 2023](#)

Discussion:

Outstanding actions were discussed with update on progress and completion.
No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed.
Sarah Jones, attending her first Council meeting was welcomed.

[RDA Draft Strategic Plan 2024-2028 – Lee Wilson](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an overview of the draft strategic plan 2024-2028 and members discussed theme descriptions, key strategic areas, and priorities for each of the four strategy pillars.

Decision:

Council members to provide feedback on the draft strategy document by 18th September 2023.

[RDA Strategic Plan Presentation at P21 / IDW 2023 – Connie Clare](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with the proposed content, steps, and timing for presenting the strategic plan to the RDA community during RDA P21 (IDW 2023), including in-person board meetings and on and off-line visibility.

Decision:

Council members agreed with the proposed steps, timing and approaches presented. Council agreed with the proposed steps and approaches presented and also approved the timeline to prepare the draft strategy document to be presented in October in conjunction with RDA P21 / IDW 2023.

[IDW 2023 Update and Overview – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an overview of the key meetings and activities to take place at IDW 2023 and a breakdown of the programme, sessions, plenary pathways, sponsors and hosts and RDA meetings specific for Council. Members discussed the registration fees and the category for LMIC participants and possible misinterpretation.

Decision:

Council members agreed that all RDA events going forward, where there is a registration fee, the LMIC category should refer to Low- and Middle-Income countries.

[TAB Elections 2023 – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update and timeline for the forthcoming Technical Advisory Board Elections in 2023.

Decision:

Council decided to extend the nomination phase by 2 weeks and shorten the election/voting phase by 2 weeks.

[AOB](#)

Next Council meeting 27 October 2023 09:00 – 15:00 – face to face in Salzburg at IDW 2023. Rebecca Koskela, rotating off as Co-chair of the Regional Advisory Board was thanked for her contribution to Council.

RDA Council Meeting
27th October 2023 UTC 07:00-13:00
Salzburg, Austria

Meeting Chair: Lee Wilson, Jill Benn

Attendees:

1. Jill Benn
2. Louise Bezuidenhout
3. Juan Bicarregui
4. Ingrid Dillo
5. Joyce Gosata Maphanyane (virtual attendance)
6. Jason Haga
7. Wolfram Horstmann
8. Sarah Jones
9. Claudia Medeiros
10. Amy Nurnberger
11. Shelley Stall
12. Martina Stockhause (on behalf of TAB co-chairs)
13. Lee Wilson
14. Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Foundation Secretary General)
15. Bridget Walker (RDA Foundation Operations & Accounts Manager) (notes)
16. Connie Clare (RDA Foundation Community Development Manager)
17. Irina Hope (RDA Foundation Global Events Manager)

Apologies: Francoise Genova, Rosie Hicks, Isabelle Perseil, Rob Quick

[Conflict of Interest, Agenda approval and actions following meeting of 7 September 2023](#)

Discussion:

Outstanding actions were discussed with an update on progress and completion. No conflicts of interest with the agenda items were expressed. Sarah Jones, Amy Nurnberger and Wolfram Horstmann were welcomed to their first in person Council meeting. Isabelle Perseil and Rob Quick, TAB co-chairs were unable to attend and Martina Stockhause, TAB member, represented TAB on their behalf. Francoise Genova and Rosie Hicks also sent their apologies on behalf of the Regional Advisory Board.

[RDA Foundation Financial Update – Juan Bicarregui, Financial Subcommittee Chair](#)

Discussion:

Council was presented with an update on the RDA Foundation cashflow summary for the period July-September 2023 and forecasts October-December 2023 and 2024 and estimates for 2025-2028. It was confirmed that the balance for each year, which includes conservative estimates for expected income, is positive.

A wind-down scenario was also presented and explained, and the financial figures remain well within the financial balance. The wind-down scenario was presented in the interests of best practice governance rather than a likelihood of wind-down in the near future.

Council discussed the need for an RDA global communications person to be employed part time from 2024 due to reduction of in-kind support from regional partners.

Decision:

Council agreed to proceeding with the recruitment of a new part time member of staff for RDA global communications.

[Technical Advisory Board Update – Martina Stockhause](#)

Discussion:

A report of TAB's face to face meeting on 22nd October 2023 was given together with activities carried out in the 2nd half of the year.

Discussion focused on a proposed system for improved communication between group co-chairs and TAB, and a proposed change to the assignment of TAB liaisons to groups, possibly increasing the number for each group. Council also discussed the issue of inactive TAB members and possible solutions and the need for improved visibility of new TAB members within the community.

Decision:

A formally written process for inactive TAB members is to be drawn up by TAB and, if approved, will be included in the RDA Governance document. Ways of increasing TAB visibility in communications and events will be identified.

[RDA Organisational Risk Assessment – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

As the RDA Foundation does not have a defined and approved risk assessment, Council discussed this with regard to the organisation itself and the RDA community and the approach to be taken.

Decision:

It was decided that a Council Risk Assessment sub-group would be set up by Hilary Hanahoe, with Shelley Stall, Amy Nurnberger, Wolfram Horstmann and Juan Bicarregui as members, with the first assessment being done in the first 6 months of 2024.

[Governance Document Check & Change – Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

Council was asked to consider whether the Governance Document, in its current form, is sufficiently comprehensive in describing the structures of the RDA, and their relationships, that support the activity and principles of the RDA, and Council's powers and authority, and whether there are sections to be updated, included, or removed. Discussions also included the current Code of Conduct policy.

Decision:

Council decided no particular amendments were required to the Governance Document at this point in time but that a process should be set up for regular reviewing which would take place once a year at a Council meeting. The RDA community would also be included through a living document providing FAQ/Q&A for all governance documents. The Code of Conduct would be reviewed and updated, particularly for when other organisations are involved, i.e. at the International Data Week event.

[RDA Web Platform update and other important updates - Hilary Hanahoe, Irina Hope](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the progress with the development of the new RDA web platform and other important updates for Council including the Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS) application, Council Elections 2024, and Virtual Plenary Meeting – 22nd RDA Plenary Meeting.

The revised timeline for the new web platform was presented, with delays to launch from 2023 to early 2024, and Council was reassured of the professionalism of the developers. Council was informed that the application to the SCOSS call this year was successful and the facilitated funding system was outlined, how it fits into the Foundation's yearly forecasts, and the general process and approach of SCOSS with its partner funders.

Council was presented with a proposed timeline for the Council elections 2024.

Council was reminded of the new policy for RDA plenaries from 2024, with one fully virtual and one hybrid per year. The plans for the fully virtual Plenary 22 were presented with the proposed dates and registration fees and the need for temporary staff to cover all time zones involved.

Decision:

Council nominations committee would be set up by Ingrid and Hilary. The suggested dates for Plenary 22 were agreed together with the investment required for temporary staff.

[RDA Strategy 2024-2028 Update – Jill Benn, Lee Wilson](#)

Discussion:

Council was provided with an update on the comments received during IDW 2023 meetings and reminded of the next steps and timeline for finalising and publishing the RDA Strategy 2024-2028.

[Regional & Organisational Advisory Board Updates – Shelley Stall, OAB, Hilary Hanahoe](#)

Discussion:

An update on the ongoing activities of the Organisational Assembly and Advisory Board (OA/B) was provided and discussions took place on the collaboration between the OA and TAB with regard to RDA group recommendations with the aim of improved synthesis and wider implementation.

An update of the Regional Assembly activities was provided by Hilary Hanahoe (in the absence of the RAB co-chairs) which included an explanation of a proposed world webinar series to support promotion of the regions and their open science and cultural activities.

AOB

Items discussed included arrangements of plenary meetings particularly when held with other organisations, consideration of a plenary highlighting RDA regional work and how multi-lingualism can be supported and offered.

A Publishers Forum was proposed and whether a coordination or Interest Group would be more appropriate were it to go ahead.

Council decided the current RDA statement on Ukraine would be updated to cover all conflict.

Council agreed to coincide the next face to face meeting with another event, possibly PIDfest in Prague in June 2024.